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APPLICATE

Advanced Prediction in Polar regions and beyond: Modelling, observing system design and Linkages associated with a Changing Arctic climaTE

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Second report on the content and extent of joint activities with collaborators in USA and Canada

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Table of Contents

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
1. INTRODUCTION	4
1.1 Background and motivation	4
2. REPORT ON JOINT ACTIVITIES WITH USA AND CANADA	4
2.1 Main partners	4
2.2 Activities involving APPLICATE team members	6
3. FURTHER REPORT	11

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

There are a number of collaborations between APPLICATE partners and groups in the USA and Canada. Effective clustering for these activities happens both in terms of science coordination as well as at scientific levels. As part of WP8 on Clustering scientific collaborations that are directly or indirectly related to the project activities have been tracked. This document, the second of three reports, contains a non-exhaustive list of activities as reported by APPLICATE partners on their current and most significant engagements with collaborators from North America.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background and motivation

Advancing polar predictive capacity in the Arctic and understanding the impact of Arctic climate change on the weather and climate in midlatitudes has attracted considerable attention in recent years. It is not surprising, thus, that there are numerous projects both in Europe and North America tackling these issues. The advantage is that there is now the critical mass needed to make much needed progress. However, in order to avoid unnecessary duplication and exploit synergies, effective clustering is needed. The clustering concept employed in the APPLICATE project for activities with partners in Europe and North America is outlined in the Clustering Plan (i.e., Milestone MS18).

There is a number of collaborations between APPLICATE partners and groups in the USA and Canada that are related to key activities of the APPLICATE project. Effective clustering for these activities happens at both coordination and scientific levels. As part of WP8 on Clustering, scientific collaborations that are directly or indirectly related to the project activities have been tracked. This document contains a non-exhaustive list of activities as reported by APPLICATE partners on their current and most significant engagements with collaborators in North America.

2. REPORT ON JOINT ACTIVITIES WITH USA AND CANADA

2.1 Main partners

APPLICATE contributes to implementing the Transatlantic Ocean Research Alliance¹ through strong collaboration with coordinating bodies and numerous individual collaborators from the US and Canada. Some partners are listed in Table 1 (updated as of October 2019) along with the main contact points.

Table 1: List of major partners in USA and Canada for which clustering activities are carried out as of October 2019 (in alphabetic order).

¹ <http://ec.europa.eu/research/iscp/index.cfm?pg=transatlantic-alliance>

Partner	Points of contact
Canada	
Environment and Climate Change Canada (ECCC)	Barbara Casati Bertrand Denis Stephane Laroche Emmanuel Poan Pierre Pellerin Gilbert Brunet Bill Merrifield
University of Toronto	Paul Kushner
Université du Québec à Montréal	Arlan Dirkson
McGill University	Bruno Tremblay
University of Ottawa	Natalie Carter
Simon Fraser University	David Hik
United States	
National Center for Atmospheric Research (NCAR)	Julio Bacmeister Gokhan Danabasoglu Andrew Gettelman Cecile Hannay Marika Holland
National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA)	Mitch Bushuk Taneil Uttal Michael Winton
Sea Ice Prediction Network (SIPN)	Cecilia Bitz Edward Blanchard- Wrigglesworth
University of California Irvine	Yannick Peings
University of Colorado	Amy Solomon
US CLIVAR Working Group on Arctic-Midlatitude Linkages	Judah Cohen Xiangdong Zhang
National Snow And Ice Data Centre (NSIDC)	Peter Pulsifer
US Arctic Commission	John Farrel

High-level coordination between the different activities is ensured by effective communication between the coordination offices of the various projects, participation/representation in each other's annual meetings, and organisation of joint events at international conferences. Scientific coordination is carried out by several individuals in the APPLICATE team.

2.2 Activities involving APPLICATE team members

APPLICATE is making a substantial contribution to the Year of Polar Prediction (YOPP)—As one of the deliverables of the Arctic Science Ministerial². For example, Arctic Climate Across Scales (ACAS) is a YOPP-endorsed project funded by the Knut and Alice Wallenberg foundation that is closely connected to APPLICATE, with one key target being the development of observation capabilities in the Arctic by deploying instruments on the Swedish icebreaker Oden. During the Swedish "Arctic Ocean 2018" (AO2018) field experiment during July and August 2018, ACAS makes its first deployment with a suite of different instruments, including 6-hourly radio soundings. The soundings are performed in collaboration with ECCC, who supply the radiosondes for this campaign. These soundings form the backbone for all the atmospheric observations and are necessary for carrying out cutting-edge research. Additionally, the 6-hourly soundings will be transmitted in near-real time to the GTS so that they can be used by operational prediction centres for carrying out improved weather forecasts. After the expedition, ECCC will use the full suite of observations from AO2018 for model evaluation and development.

Stockholm University (Gunilla Svensson) and Jonathan Day (ECMWF) have a close collaboration with ECCC (Barbara Casati), NOAA (Taneil Uttal) and the University of Colorado (Amy Solomon) as part of the YOPP supersite Model Intercomparison Project (YOPPsiteMIP). The aim of this YOPP initiative is to evaluate forecast performance evaluation at polar supersites. The Arctic supersites used for the exercise are mainly the IASOA (International Arctic Systems for Observing the Atmosphere) network which is coordinated by Taneil Uttal. This work aligns with the goals of APPLICATE to find model biases in processes as well as will possibly lead to identification of cases that can be used within APPLICATE for intercomparison of models on a process level. The inter-comparison includes several of the APPLICATE NWP models (IFS HRES from ECMWF and AROME from Meteo France and MET Norway) in addition to the Canadian ECCC CAPS and a number of NOAA forecast models set up for YOPP. As part of YOPP these partners are performing evaluation of their models at polar super-sites. This involves several APPLICATE partners: ECMWF, Met Norway, University of Stockholm, Meteo France and the Met Office. It will also include collaboration with North American Partners ECCC and NOAA, including members of the IASOA network.

Since D8.8 was submitted the following has been achieved:

- The YOPPsiteMIP experiment description was published on the PPP-YOPP website.
- The YOPPsiteMIP concept was presented at:
 - YOPP-IASC Arctic Science Summit (Helsinki, Finland, Jan 2019)

² <https://www.iarpcollaborations.org/news/9953>

- MOSAiC workshop (Potsdam, Germany, May 2019)
- YOPP-SH meeting (Charlston, USA, Jun 2019)
- IUGG (Montreal, Canada, Jul 2019)
- Working Group for Numerical Experimentation (Offenbach, Sep 2019)
- Forecast datasets from ECMWF, Meteo-France and ECCC have been archived at Met Norway and made available via the YOPP-Portal. Other modelling centres are committed to do the same over the coming year.
- A prototype Merged Observatory Data File (MODF) has been produced for Barrow, Alaska by NOAA colleagues to meet the needs of YOPPsiteMIP.
- YOPPsiteMIP workshop was held at the University of Stockholm (17-19th September 2020) with 15 scientists in attendance, including several APPLICATE scientists and the North American experts mentioned above, to plan the analysis and publications for the project.

Jonathan Day also delivered a lecture on sea ice predictability and prediction at the NCAR Polar Climate Modeling workshop, held in Boulder in August this year.

Work Package 4 in APPLICATE works to provide guidance for a better exploitation of current observing systems in the Arctic and for making recommendations for future optimizations, in order to improve sub-seasonal to interannual Arctic and lower-latitude predictions. Work Package 5 extends the work done in WP4, by quantifying the improved skill provided through APPLICATE, and is expected to provide general guidance for weather and climate predictions in the Arctic and beyond. This will include a systematic benchmarking of APPLICATE's predictions with respect to existing databases. So far, the following activities have been undertaken with US or Canadian partners in relationship to WP4/WP5 activities:

- A study on methodological aspects of sea-ice data assimilation, involving Prof Cecilia Bitz from the University of Washington, has been published in *Tellus A* (Kimmritz et al., 2018). The study provides recommendations for the design of initialization methods in large-scale climate models. More generally, four institutions (UCL, BSC, NERSC and UW) exchange regularly on topics related to sea-ice data assimilation in order to learn from each other's experience. Another publication is currently under revision (Zhang et al., 2018). In addition, fraternal experiments are planned within the next year, that is, experiments in which data generated by one climate model is assimilated into another.
- Thomas Jung and Francois Massonnet are both still involved in the Sea Ice Prediction Network 2 (SIPN2) leadership team. SIPN2 is a US-based initiative to collect and analyse seasonal outlooks of Arctic sea ice from various sources. One of the goals of APPLICATE WP5 is to evaluate the skill of EC-Earth, CNRM, Met Office and ECMWF relative that of the forecasts provided through the SIPN2 database, which includes far more models and various different forecast approaches (e.g. empirical vs dynamical). These SIPN2 data will be used in the skill score Atlas, which is an APPLICATE deliverable due in October 2018 summarising the current status of weather and prediction in the Arctic, and in which the US SIPN2 group collaborates. Furthermore, some APPLICATE partners will contribute to SIPN2 with their own seasonal predictions.

ECMWF is coordinating numerical experimentation aiming to understand the role of Arctic observations in numerical weather prediction systems and to guide the design of future observing systems in polar regions. This numerical experimentation relies on Observing System Experiments (OSEs), in which the certain observation types are removed from the data assimilation system used to create the initial conditions for the weather forecasts. Environment Canada (ECCC) and ECMWF performed an extended set of OSEs for a winter and a summer period, which include the Special Observing Periods of YOPP, in which different observing systems are denied in polar regions (north of 60N and south of 60S). The OSEs were performed with their global NWP systems, albeit run at a lower resolution than that used for their operational medium-range forecasts (i.e. 25 instead of 9km for ECMWF, and 39 instead of 25km for ECCC). DWD also performed a limited set of OSEs for the winter SOP with their global NWP system at the operational resolution (13km). Met Norway focuses on the impact of Arctic observations in their limited area NWP system, and has performed a wide range of OSEs aimed at understanding the impact of observations both through assimilation in the limited area data assimilation system, and through their use in the global NWP system (the ECMWF Integrated Forecast System) used to provide lateral boundary conditions for the limited area system. Results are discussed on a regular basis (every couple of months) via teleconferences. These experiments and exchanges have demonstrated that:

- current polar observing systems clearly have positive impacts for short and medium-range forecast skill both in polar regions and mid-latitudes;
- conventional observations are the most influential observing system during winter (for Arctic and mid-latitudes) in all global models (ECCC, ECMWF, DWD);
- in regional NWP systems, polar observations clearly have positive impacts on forecast skill both through direct assimilation and via the lateral boundary conditions;
- the importance/ranking of each observing system depends on the use of observations in the respective NWP system (there are differences in the assimilation systems used, e.g. 4D-Var/4d-EnVar/3D-Var, and some key differences in satellite data usage over sea-ice/snow, clear-sky vs all-sky);
- the impacts of observations on forecast skill are always subject to the sophistication/maturity of the data use. Investment in the data use may be at least as important as investment in further observations. In particular, forecast skill could be gained by better exploiting the satellite observations over snow and sea-ice. It is important to keep in mind that good models, observations usage and data assimilation techniques are all key for making an effective use of observations in data assimilation systems used to create the initial conditions for the forecasts.

The results of the OSEs performed at ECMWF are summarized in two recent publications, Lawrence et al. QJRM, 2019 and Day et al., QJRM, 2019. Results at ECCC and MetNo are also being summarized in publications. Day et al. (2019) used the OSEs and diagnostic techniques to analyse the linkages between the Arctic and mid-latitudes during the winter period. More precisely, they have demonstrated that removing observations from the data assimilation system used to create the initial conditions for the forecasts has an impact on the predictive skill in the mid-latitudes especially during periods of Scandinavian blocking. Colleagues at ECCC are now performing a similar analysis, using complementary diagnostic methods, for the summer period. They are exploring Arctic to

mid-latitude linkages using OSEs and ensemble weather forecasts performed both at ECCO and ECMWF. ECCO will also use Forecast Sensitivity to Observations (FSOI) diagnostics relying on their ensemble forecasts to explore the impact of observations on short-range forecasts. This study will complement the FSOI analysis done at ECMWF (Lawrence et al., QJRM, 2019) which relied on adjoint techniques.

Pablo Ortega (BSC) was invited to participate in the [webinars](#) of the Sea Ice Prediction Network Phase 2 (SIPN2), to disseminate APPLICATE and the Seasonal Prediction activities performed within WP5. The talk dealt with topics like the added value of resolution on the seasonal prediction skill, the development of forecast biases during the first month of prediction, the use of statistical models as a benchmark for the dynamical predictions, and a skill assessment with all the seasonal forecast systems contributing to APPLICATE. Likewise, Uma Bhatt (University of Alaska Fairbanks), the PI of SIPN2, was also invited to participate in the last WP5 telco, in which she introduced SIPN2 and related activities to WP5 partners. CNRS-GAME and BSC have established a collaboration with Environment Canada (Gregory Smith, Andrew Peterson and Hai Lin) to perform a coordinated study of the impact of model resolution on the seasonal forecast skill, with a specific focus on the Arctic regions and the linkages with the mid-latitudes. The analysis will include the two LR (1° in ocean) and HR (i.e. $1/4^\circ$ in the ocean) seasonal forecast systems included in APPLICATE (MeteoFrance and EC-Earth) as well as the CanCM seasonal forecast system (1° ocean) and monthly forecast system ($1/4^\circ$ ocean). A preliminary study is planned to be included in D5.3, focused on the added value on skill during november for key variables such as sea ice concentrations, sea level pressure, surface air temperature and precipitation. Environment Canada colleagues offer to extend some of their monthly forecasts beyond 1 month to be able to assess the prediction capacity of their HR system in winter as well.

Ed Blockley (MetOffice) attended the IGS sea ice symposium in Winnipeg in August 2019 and presented preliminary work from our SIMIP Arctic sea ice mass budget inter-comparison that is being undertaken within APPLICATE T1.4. Furthermore, SIMIP mass budget inter-comparison led by MetOffice is gaining interest from organisations based in US/Canada with contributions from two US partners, CSEM/NCAR (David Bailey) and GFDL (Mitch Bushuk), and from Environment and Climate Change Canada (Neil Swart).

There has been a very fruitful collaboration between the NorESM-group at MET Norway and the US CESM-program centred around NCAR. The Norwegian Earth System Model (NorESM) is an amended version of the Community Earth System Models (CESMs) developed at a number of universities and science labs in the US. The definition of and production runs with CESM are co-ordinated by the National Center of Atmospheric Research (NCAR) in Boulder, Colorado. The NorESM-group keeps a close contact with NCAR and the CESM-groups, both on a scientific and a technical level. On a quasi-regular basis, the contacts are by e-mail, sometimes by telecons, and by participation in annual working group meetings (AMWG and CCWG in February 2017 and 2018), and in the annual CESM general workshop (June 2017). The main contact points at NCAR are the CESM Chief Scientist (up to Jan 2018: J-F. Lamarque; at present: Gokhan Danabasoglu) and the Working-Group Chairs (in particular AMWG, up to Jan 2018 Rich

Neale, at present Julio Bacmeister; and the WAWG, Andrew Gettelman). With respect to polar climate issues, Marika Holland is the main contact point, and there are regular contacts on scientific and technical issues with several, in particular with Cecile Hannay for the development of the CMIP6-version.

Météo France (Rym Msadek) is collaborating with NOAA GFDL in Princeton, USA on sea ice predictability in the Arctic. More specifically they have been working closely with Mitch Bushuk and Michael Winton at GFDL to evaluate the regional skill of Arctic sea ice the GFDL seasonal predictions (see their joint paper in GRL: <https://doi.org/10.1002/2017GL073155>). They also conducted a comprehensive work to compare this regional skill in operational predictions obtained using a perfect model framework, which allows to identify where progress is possible to improve the regional forecasts Arctic with better models and a better initialization. The paper has been revised and is being accepted. This work is not directly funded by APPLICATE but it is relevant to WP5. Mitch Bushuk visited Météo France in Toulouse in March 2017 to discuss possible collaboration to compare the seasonal forecasts of GFDL to those produced by Météo France. Rym Msadek has also initiated a collaboration that started with Canada to cooperate on projects related to sea ice variability and the role of sea ice in climate changes. CERFACS is currently hosting Prof. Bruno Tremblay from McGill University.

Furthermore, in 2013 Météo France signed a MoU with Environment and Climate Change Canada (ECCC) to develop a cooperation on meteorology, hydrology and oceanography, which is still ongoing. Under this agreement, there are actual collaborations on ocean-sea ice forecasts (including sea ice modelling and coupling with the atmosphere), snow observations and modelling, and subseasonal to seasonal forecasting (including, but not limited to, projects S2S and FRAMS). These collaborations include sharing of expertise, code, data and also scientific visits.

Météo France has also shown interest in contributing to the project FRAMS (Forecasting Regional Arctic Sea Ice from a Month to Seasons) coordinated by Bruno Tremblay (McGill University) and Bertrand Denis (ECCC), funded by the MEOPAR Canadian network. Contribution includes sharing outputs from MF seasonal forecasting system, to serve a proof of concept for the Arctic RCC long range forecasting capabilities.

APPLICATE coordinator Thomas Jung (AWI) and WP3-leader Doug Smith (MetOffice) participated in the US CLIVAR Working Group on Arctic Change and Possible Influence on Mid-Latitude Climate and Weather working group. As the US CLIVAR working group has finished its term in early summer 2018, the APPLICATE team will continue clustering with North American partners in the framework of the PAMIP team, which is co-lead by the APPLICATE-PI Doug Smith. In this framework, in June 2019 a three-day international workshop to discuss the first results of the PAMIP was held at Dartington Hall, Devon, UK. There were 40 attendees, including APPLICATE and Blue Action partners and scientists from USA, Canada, Japan, Australia and Korea.

A collaboration by MET Norway, ECMWF, Météo France and ECCC in the framework of YOPP verification task team and APPLICATE performed a NWP model-intercomparison in APPLICATE resulting in the paper:

Køltzow, M., B. Casati, E. Bazile, T. Haiden, and T. Valkonen, 2019: An NWP Model Intercomparison of Surface Weather Parameters in the European Arctic during the Year of Polar Prediction Special Observing Period Northern Hemisphere 1. *Wea. Forecasting*, 34, 959–983, <https://doi.org/10.1175/WAF-D-19-0003.1>.

Currently, MET Norway, ECCC and ECMWF are also working on a joint paper on the verification of solid precipitation within the framework of the YOPP verification task team and APPLICATE.

Laurent Terray (CERFACS) is an external collaborator of the CanSISE project, coordinated by Paul Kushner from U. Toronto. The Canadian Sea Ice and Snow Evolution (CanSISE) Network is a 5-year collaborative partnership between researchers from eight Canadian universities (Toronto, York, McGill, Victoria, Guelph, Waterloo, UBC, UNBC) and three partner organizations (the Climate Research Division of Environment Canada, the Canadian Ice Service, and the Pacific Climate Impacts Consortium). The CanSISE Network seeks to advance seasonal to multidecadal prediction of Arctic sea ice and snow in Canada’s sub-Arctic, alpine, and seasonally snow covered regions. It will also quantify and exploit, for prediction purposes, the role that Northern Hemisphere snow and sea ice processes play in climate variability and change.

APECS, in coordination with the offices of the Year of Polar Prediction, organized a joint APECS-YOPP-APPLICATE [Online Course](#) on “**Advancing Predictive Capability of Northern Hemisphere Weather and Climate**” directed to early career scientists to examine in depth topics, issues and skills related to Arctic weather and climate prediction modelling. The course will last from September 19th to December 5th with weekly appointments divided into four thematic blocs. The organization involved a colleague from the University of Ottawa, Natalie Carter, and the list of lecturers includes Taneil Uttal from NOAA (U.S.A.), Barbara Casati from Environment and Climate Change Canada and Alran Dirkson from Université du Québec à Montréal. Among the attendees, several students and early career scientists from the US and Canada registered for the course.

3. FURTHER REPORT

Monitoring of clustering activities with USA and Canada will be carried out by the WP8 leaders. Another final report on these activities will be produced in the fourth year of the project (i.e., D8.10 due month 48).